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Research Article

**A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF QUALITY OF LIFE IN
WOMEN WITH WANTED AND UNWANTED PREGNANCY
AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS**¹Dr.Eisha tur Raazia and ²Dr.Nosheen Niazi¹King Edward Medical college Lahore²Army Medical College Rawalpindi**Abstract:**

Introduction: Unwanted pregnancy causes mental and psychological distresses and also some changes in women's personal and social life which can influence their quality of life. The present research aims to compare quality of life of women with wanted and unwanted pregnancy.

Methods and procedures: Descriptive-analytical study was conducted on 318 pregnant women in the Gyn and Obst wards of Services Hospital Lahore. The questionnaire under study was WHOQOL-BREF and statistical analysis was done by SPSS 18 and statistical test χ^2 square test and Student's *t*-test.

Results: The score of life quality of women with unwanted pregnancy was 70.53 ± 8.40 and score of women with wanted pregnancy was equal to 75.03 ± 9.34 and this difference was statistically significant ($p=0.01$). Average score of life quality in physical ($p=0.04$), environmental ($p=0.03$), social ($p=0.04$) sub-scales in women with unwanted pregnancy was less than those with wanted pregnancy and this decrease was statistically significant.

Conclusion: with respect to the effect of unwanted pregnancy on life quality of pregnant women, reducing the prevalence of unwanted pregnancies should be at the top of health care providers' programs.

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INTRODUCTION:

Pregnancy is a common event in women in fertility ages and it influences women comprehensively¹. Approximately 175 million of pregnancies are annually recorded all around the world from which 75 million ones are unwanted (2). According to a study, 61 percent births are unwanted (3). Unwanted pregnancy is a risky field for the deaths of mothers and children, because if unwanted pregnancy continues, it will increase mental pressure on mother and this issue will lead to lack of sufficient care of themselves and the fetus consequently, unwanted pregnancy influences two major indicators of mothers and children's death. So, unwanted pregnancy is a threat for mother and child's health and it is considered as reason of increasing their death and a major barrier for improving fertility and sexual health⁴. Unwanted pregnancy has caused stress, depression and suicide in women and it increases misbehavior and negligence in child care (5). Loss job, divorce and instability in emotional relationship and high rate of abortion have been reported in women with unwanted pregnancy and women start health care of pregnancy period later⁶. Planned pregnancy makes birth of child more pleasurable for mother and creates a more emotional relationship between the mother and the child, in the other words, unwanted pregnancy influences quality of life⁷. The quality of life at all stages of life including pregnancy time and after childbirth can be assessed (8). Life quality includes person's different dimensions of physical, mental and social health and comfort. Evaluation of life quality in planning for mothers and infants care and understanding and perceiving the necessity of existence of these cares are important for policy makers and associations of health care⁹. Fertility health is one of the effective factors on life quality related to women health. Schwartz's study in 2008 showed that the effects of unwanted pregnancy on life quality of women are so much that it must be integrated into the cost of effectiveness analysis and efficiency of family planning programs (10).

Other studies also emphasize the effect of unwanted pregnancy on life quality (11-12). Despite the fact that life quality plays a significant role in pregnant women's health, few studies have been conducted on life quality and unwanted pregnancy. A limited number of studies have been also conducted in this regard and mostly, prevalence and effective factors on incidence of unwanted pregnancy and its consequences on mother and child have been more investigated. The present research aims to compare life quality of pregnant women with wanted and unwanted pregnancy.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

This paper was a descriptive-analytical study by simple and accessible sampling method so that 318 persons were entered into study among pregnant mothers referring to prenatal care clinics according to entry criteria. Entry criteria included age from 16 to 40 years, lack of mental, medical, midwifery problems and experience of severe stressful incidents in the past 6 months and lack of drug and cigar abuse. The method of completing the World Health Organization's quality of life questionnaire was taught to these women following explaining and obtaining informed consent from them. WHOQIL-BREFI 26 –questions, questionnaire was used to assess quality of life. This questionnaire's questions are related to evaluation of life quality and its variables which includes four dimensions of life quality in addition to two general questions regarding evaluation of life quality and health.

The structure of mentioned questionnaire's questions related to its four areas is as follows:

- 1- Physical health (activity level in daily life, dependency to drug and therapeutic goals, ability to move, pain and discomfort, sleep and rest and ability to do including questions number 3, 4, 10, 15, 16, 17, 18).
- 2- Psychological health (spirituality, religion and personal beliefs, positive and negative feelings, thinking, memory and focus including questions number 5, 6, 7, 11, 19, 26).
- 3- Environmental health (financial resources, access to hygiene and social care with appropriate quality, physical safe and security including questions number 8, 9, 12, 13, 14, 24, 25).
- 4- Social relations (personal relations, social support and sexual performance including questions number 20, 21, 22).

According to information of World Health Organization's scoring, minimum scores of each area has been set 4 and maximum number is 20 and the scores can be converted to scale zero up to 100. The score of each area is set to 0-100 in questionnaire's guide and higher score indicates better condition and lower one indicates more problems in that area¹³. This questionnaire has been validated by Sahar Naz Nejjat et al and values of Cronbach's alpha correlation in all areas have been obtained higher than 70% and its reliability has been desirably confirmed¹⁴. Statistical analysis was done by SPSS (version 18) and descriptive statistic test and t-test and chi-square test and significance level

was considered $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

The results showed that the most unwanted pregnancy had happened women with high school education with 44.4 percent, on the other hand, there was a statistically significant relationship between unwanted pregnancy and previous abortion history ($p=0.007$) and number of children ($p=0.008$) and previous childbirth method ($p=0.01$) (Table 1).

In this study, 318 pregnant women were in average age of 20.76 ± 4.23 . 47.8 percent of women were spending their first pregnancy. 37.9 percent of them were educated at university and

majority of them were housekeeper. 88.7 percent of women had wanted pregnancy and 11.3 percent of them had unwanted one.

The average gained score of life quality in women with wanted pregnancy was equal to 75.03 ± 9.34 and that of unwanted pregnancy was equal to $70.538.40$. Statistical t-test showed the significant relationship between two groups ($p=0.01$). On the other hand, there was a statistically significant relationship between all the life quality's dimensions of pregnant women except psychological dimension based on comparison of average of all dimensions (Table 2).

Table 1: Characteristics of participants and association of these characteristics with unintended pregnancy Values from Chi-square test.

Characteristics		Planned pregnancy Mean \pm SD or n (%)	Unintended pregnancy	P value
Age		20.87 \pm 4.32	20.08 \pm 3.36	
Educational level	Uneducated	11(3.9)	2(5.6)	0.6
	Primary school	63(22.4)	6(16.7)	
	Secondary school	99(35.2)	16(44.4)	
	College or University	108(38.4)	12(33.3)	
Employment status	Housewife	250(88.7)	31(86.1)	0.4
	Employed	32(11.3)	5(13.9)	
Previous Abortion	Yes	41(14.5)	241(85.5)	0.007
	NO	12(33.3)	24(66.7)	
Number of child	0	143(50.7)	12(33.3)	0.008
	1-3	135(47.9)	21(58.3)	
	>3	4(1.4)	3(8.3)	
Previous delivery	Nuliparouse	145(51.4)	9(25)	0.01
	NVD	53(18.8)	16(44.4)	
	Caesarian section	84(29.8)	11(30.6)	

Table 2: The compression Domain quality of life between unintended pregnancy and planned pregnancy Values from T-test.

Domain	Planned pregnancy Mean \pm SD	Unintended pregnancy Mean \pm SD	p
physical health	21.96 \pm 5.07	20.27 \pm 3.63	0.04
Psychological	17.39 \pm 2.54	17.05 \pm 2.49	0.4
environmental health	24.80 \pm 4.64	23.03 \pm 4.78	0.03
social relationships	10.78 \pm 2.21	10.00 \pm 2.30	0.04
Total quality of life	75.03 \pm 9.34	70.53 \pm 8.40	0.01

DISCUSSION:

Unwanted pregnancy was seen in 11.3 percent of units under study in this research. The rate of unwanted pregnancy in research's results of Mortazavi et al in 2011 was 12 percent(15) which was consistent with our study that was very lower as compared to last two decades. The results of a meta-analysis regarding prevalence of unwanted pregnancy in two last decade showed that this rate gas been equal to 29.7 percent (16). In a meta-analysis study, unwanted pregnancy rate was 30.6% (17). There are different rate of prevalence

in other countries. This rate has been announced 24 percent in Ikamari (18), 36.5 percent in a study (19) and 49 percent in the study of Lawrence and Ventura (20-21). The reason of this decrease may be due to decrease in rate of population growth in the last two decades. On the other hand, the different rate of prevalence is due to difference in awareness, attitude and performance in women regarding methods of preventing from pregnancy in different locations (22, 23).

There was relationship between number of children and unwanted pregnancy in the present

study ($p=0.008$). A direct relationship has been confirmed in study of Asadi et al (24). The study of Tatum et al has also mentioned this relation (19). The study of Jarahe et al showed that there is a significant relationship between unwanted pregnancy and number of children ($p = 0.04$) and the number of previous pregnancies ($p = 0.01$) (25). This can be because of this fact that the women who have reached the desired number of children are more likely to consider repeated pregnancy as unwanted one. The study's results showed that 66.6 percent of women with unwanted pregnancy declared a previous abortion history. Several studies have referred to relationship between unwanted pregnancy cases and increase in abortion (26, 27). It seems that pregnant women with unwanted pregnancy consider abortion as the first strategy for terminate pregnancy.

In the present study, life quality in women with unwanted pregnancy was at a lower level compared with mothers with wanted pregnancy. In study of Schmieg et al, quality of life in women with unwanted pregnancy has been decreased (28). The study's findings of Abbaszadeh show that the women with unwanted pregnancy have 25 times more chance for having life with lower quality which is consistent with our research (29). Unwanted and unplanned pregnancy influences not only overall life quality of pregnant women, but also its dimensions. As it was observed in present study, all the dimensions of life quality in women with unwanted pregnancy have been decreased. But in paper of Zahedi et al, incidence of mental disorders and social problems has been more common in mothers with unwanted pregnancy (9). Also The Study of Khajehpour et al showed that women with unwanted pregnancy compare women with wanted pregnancy have lower mental and physical health (30). However, a volume of more samples with enough number of wanted and unwanted pregnancy are required in order to determine accurate effect of this variable on life quality score in its different dimensions.

CONCLUSION:

Generally, since the results of present study indicate low quality of life of women with unwanted pregnancy compared with wanted ones. The study of Khajehpour et al and Schmieg et al showed quality of life in unwanted pregnancy women was lower than wanted pregnancy women (28, 30). On the other hand, Kazemi et al, Mentioned that unwanted pregnancy is one of the factors affecting on the quality of life (31). Ali showed that Mean scores of mental and physical component summary were lower in the unwanted pregnancy group compared to women

with wanted pregnancy ($p < 0.001$) (32). All of these studies are in line with our study. According to the results of this study and studies in line with this, supervisors and politicians of women's health promotion should take the necessary measures by formulating specific programs and certain actions to prevent unwanted pregnancies. Since unwanted pregnancy is one of the main indicators of qualitative evaluation of family health services that affects fertility health in all physical, mental and social dimensions, therefore, monitoring the quality of life of women with unwanted pregnancy and planning some interventions in order to improve their quality of life is essential.

Conflict of Interest: There is no conflict of interest for this research work.

REFERENCES:

1. Cunningham F, Leveno K, Bloom S, Haultz J, Gilstrap L, Wenstrom K, Williams obstetrics, 23 ed, McGraw Hill, New York, 2010.
2. Gheisarian I. Evaluation of aging phenomenon in social and economic section in Iran. J population 2010; 69(70):1-28. (Persian).
3. Amani F, Bashiri J, Nahan Moghadam N, Tabarraie Y. [Application of logistic regression model in surveying effective causes of unwanted pregnancy (Persian)]. Qom University of Medical Sciences Journal. 2010; 4(1): 32-6
4. Mumah J, Karoline CW, Izugbara CH, Mukira C. Coping with unintended pregnancies narrative from adolescents' Nairobi slums. J African population and health research centers 2014.
5. Azizi A, Amirian F, Pashaei T, Amirian M. Prevalence of unwanted pregnancy and its relationship with health-related quality of life for pregnant women's in Salas city, Kermanshah, Iran. Iranian Journal of Obstetrics, Gynecology and Infertility. 2011; 14(5): 24-29.
6. Monea E, Thomas A. Unintended Pregnancy and Taxpayer Spending. J perspective on sexual and reproductive health 2011; 43(2):88-93.
7. Pesavento F, Marconcini E, Drago D. Quality of life and depression in normal and in high-risk pregnancy: analysis of a sample of 100 women. Minerva Gynecol 2005; 57(4):451-60.
8. Jansen AJ, Duvekot JJ, Hop WC, Essink-Bot ML, Beckers EA, Karsdorp VH, et al. New insights into fatigue and health-related quality of life after delivery. Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand 2007; 86(5):579-40.
9. Zahedi M, Deris F. The quality of life in

- pregnant women in Farokhshahr city, 2012. *Journal of Clinical Nursing and Midwifery*. 2014; 3(3): 63-69..
10. Schwarz EB, Smith R, Steinauer J, Reeves MF, Caughey AB. Measuring the effects of unintended pregnancy on women's quality of life. *Contraception* 2008 Sep;78(3):204- 10.
 11. Bond SC. Effects of Unintended Pregnancy on Women's Quality of Life are varied, but more precision and Consistency Needed in Measurement. *J Midwifery & Women's Health* 2009;54(1):90.
 12. Sable MR, Washington CC, Schwartz LR, Jorgenson M. Social well-being in pregnant women: intended versus unintended pregnancies. *J PsychosocNursMent Health Serv* 2007 Dec;45(12):24-31.
 13. Webster J, Nicholas C, Velacott C, Cridland N, Fawcett L, Validation of the WHOQOL-BREF among women following childbirth, *Aust N Z J ObstetGynaecol* 2010 Apr;50(2):132-7.
 14. Nedjat S, Montazeri A, Holakouie K, Mohammad K, Majdzadeh R, Psychometric properties of the Iranian interview-administered version of the World Health Organization's Quality of Life Questionnaire (WHOQOL-BREF): a population-based study, *BMC Health Serv Res* 2008;8:61.
 15. Mortazavi F, Mousavi SA, Chaman R, khosravi A, davarzani M. Maternal Quality of life in women with wanted and unwanted pregnancy: a longitudinal study. *The journal of research committee of students at sabzevar university of medical sciences*. 2015;3(31):1-12
 16. Najafi F, Iranfar SH, Rezaii M, Iranfar KH, A meta-analysis and systematic review of the unintended pregnancy prevalence in Iran (1995-2008), *J of Kermanshah University of Medical Sciences* 2012;16(4):280-87.
 17. Moosazadeh M, Nekoei-moghadam M, Emrani Z, Amiresmaili M. Prevalence of unwanted pregnancy in Iran: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Health Plann Manage*. 2014;29(3):277-90. doi: 10.1002
 18. Ikamari L, Izugbara C, Ochako R. prevalence and determinants of unintended pregnancy among women in Nairobi Kenya. *J Pregnancy and childbirth* 2013;69(13).
 19. Teshom F, Hailu AG, Teklehaymanot AN. Prevalence of unintended pregnancy and associated factors among married pregnant women in Ganjiworeda west Wollega Oromia region, Ethiopia. *J Science of Public Health* 2014; 2(2): 92-101.
 20. Lawrence B F, Mia RZ. Unintended pregnancy in the United States: incidence and disparities. *J Original Research Article in Contraception*. 2011; 84(5):478-85.
 21. Ventura SJ, Curtin SC, Abma JC, Henshaw SK. Estimated pregnancy rates and rate pregnancy outcome for the United States, 1990-2008. *natl vital stat report*. 2012;60(7):1-22
 22. Singh S, Prada E, Kestler E. Induced abortion and unintended pregnancy in Guatemala. *Int Fam Plan Perspect* 2006 Sep; 32(3):136-45.
 23. Matteson KA, Peipert JF, Allsworth J, Phipps MG, Redding CA. Unplanned pregnancy: does past experience influence the use of a contraceptive method? *ObstetGynecol* 2006 Jan; 107(1):121-7.
 24. Asadi Y, Meshkat M, Talaei B. Unwanted pregnancy and its influencing factors in pregnant women referring to health centers of Mashhad. *J Medical science* 2007; 3 (10):91-95.
 25. Jarahi L, Zavar A, Neematshah M. Investigating unwanted pregnancy and Factors Related in pregnant women in Sarakhs. *IJOGI*, Vol. 17, No. 124, pp. 8-14, Nov 2014, p:8-14
 26. Jarahi L, Meysamie A. P, FayazBakhsh A. Assessment of Attitude and Knowledge about Intentional Abortion in Pre-married Females. *Qom University of Medical Sciences Journal*, 2012; 6(1):54-59.
 27. Maurice O, Francis T, Kwame A. Multinomial regression Analysis of unplanned pregnancies in AhafoAno South district: Ghana. *J American international journal of contemporary research* .2012 ; 2(12):90-7.
 28. Schmiege S, Russo NF. Depression and unwanted first pregnancy: longitudinal cohort study. *BMJ* 2005 ;331(7528):1303.
 29. Abbaszadeh F, Bagheri A, Mehran N. [Quality of life in pregnant women (Persian)]. *Payesh*. 2010; 9(1):69-75.
 30. Khajepour M, Simbar M, Jannesari S, Ramezani-Tehrani Fc., Majd H.A. Health status of women with intended and unintended pregnancies. *publ ic health*. 2013 1 2(7):5 8-6 4.
 31. Kazemi F, Nahidi F, Kariman N. Assessment Scales, Associated Factors and the Quality of Life Score in Pregnant Women in Iran. *Global Journal of Health Science* 2016; 8(11):.127-139.
 32. Ali A. Relationship between Unwanted Pregnancy and Health-Related Quality of Life in Pregnant Women. *J Coll Physicians Surg Pak*. 2016;26(6):507-12. doi: 2352